

REVIEW ARTICLE

Of Appropriate

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Abstract

An author writes. It is his democratic right. He writes what he thinks appropriate. An editor publishes. It is also his democratic right. An editor may not publish any writing. It is his more democratic right. In this regard an author should not mind anything. He should not pass any bad remarks against the editor. He should not propagate any adverse comments against the journal. An editor receives many articles. He compares all submissions. He publishes those articles which he thinks appropriate for his journal. He has to face tough competition with his rivals. Rubbish publication defames a journal. It experiences the dogma of sub-standard which cannot be compensated easily and regain its previous status as well. The author does not know all such matters. He should submit appropriate submission. Here lies the uniqueness of appropriate rather than unique appropriate.

Keywords: Appropriate, Suitable, Proper, Right

Introduction

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

Article

Appropriate is suitable or proper in the circumstances. For example: This isn't the appropriate time or place. It is suitable or right for a particular situation or occasion. For example: I didn't think these comments were very appropriate at the time. It is to take something for one's own use, typically without the owner's permission. For example: The accused had appropriated the property. It is to set apart for or assign to a particular purpose or use e.g., appropriate money for a research program.

All persons are not of equal merit and mentality. As such what is considered as appropriate by someone may not be so to another one. Further what is appropriate to a society may not be same to another society. Even what is accepted, as appropriate, by someone in the morning may not be accepted by that very person in the evening of that very day. Thus time also controls appropriate.

Like person appropriate depends upon various factors. A person may take something in absence of anybody. He may not agree to accept in presence of all. Bribe falls in this category. Further he may accept anything in presence of someone and may oppose in presence of another one. Love and kiss fall in this category. A sensible person is cautious for image. He values it more than money. As such he wants not to render it dirty.

Different persons behave differently. Different persons speak differently. Similarly different persons react differently. Thus exposure discloses the status of any concerned person. Further different stimuli offer identical outcome. This outcome is based on different angles or point of view. All are appropriate in different contexts.

Someone expresses with gesture and posture. He considers it appropriate. It may not be so in all cultures. Obviously, restless movement of a child is allowed in all societies. If a child is not naughty but calm by nature then he is ill-famed as manly. Manly behavior is not appropriate for a child hence not welcomed.

There is dress conduct. So, casual dress is not appropriate in any social gathering. The dress which is allowed in case of male members may not be allowed where women are present. Similarly, in case of school, office, hotel, police, defence, etc. the uniform is

unique. Every member must wear it appropriately for identification purpose. It strengthens bondage among the members.

Similarly, behavior with man may be casual but that with women should be polite and respect as well. All are equal. But in civic society women are more equal.

Drinking wine is allowed in some societies. It may not be allowed in another society in presence of senior citizens.

Approach is very important anywhere. Politeness enriches it. Sometimes it conquers the head and heart of the opponent even.

Appearance is important in interview. Here smartness both in dress and speech pave the way to get the assignment. Presence of mind is very crucial for the success.

Complexion is vital in glamour world. Here vital statistics count much. Strong personality coupled with avoidance of allurements confirm the security. Here talent of the heroine escorts to the peak. She enjoys popularity for long. Thus appropriate handling of different issues are liable for the outcome.

Silence is appropriate in any religious organization. Silence is also solicited in no horn zone i.e., hospital, court, educational institution, etc. In some societies vulgar language and attitude are allowed. Here free sex is very common. Unmarried girls become pregnant before marriage. Here single mother or single father does not suffer from social dogma. In some orthodox societies all these are strictly prohibited and are considered as crime. In such a conservative society parents select life partner. Disobedience of custom confirms honor killing.

Among everything respect is the greatest tool. It confirms reciprocation of respect coupled with help as bonus.

If someone fails to achieve something then it is clear that his strategy was not appropriate for this success. Someone finds faults with himself. Someone finds faults with others. Both the persons are diagonally opposite with each other. The former is wise and shines in life. The latter one is a fool and can do nothing. He suffers from cradle to coffin. The wise knows that the world does not adjust with anybody rather one has to adjust with the world for his mere existence.

Appropriate may be right or wrong. Similarly it may be legal or illegal. There are two types of persons. The first category always approaches through right path and in legal way. He will never adopt any unfair means to fulfill his desire. He never surrenders to any allurements. He always plays in straight bat. The second category, from the very beginning, adopts the unfair means i.e. wrong and illegal avenue to reach the desired goal. For this he uses either muscle power or money or both simultaneously as per demand of the situation. The former has the bonafide intention and the latter one has malafide intention respectively.

Besides these two extreme categories there is another category viz., third category. Such a person of third category wants to realize his ambition by hook or by crook. His strategy is a cocktail of both good and bad. Firstly he tries in honest means. If it does not serve the purpose then he adopts the dishonest avenue. His strategy is that he wants to return home with the baton of success i.e. desired thing in hand. A maniac person may not decide anything as appropriate. He always suffers from indecision. He suffers from baseless fear. Similarly, it is very difficult to satisfy a moody person.

A girl may be foodie, moody and choosy. She is not satisfied whatever is offered to her. She always rejects. Nothing is appropriate to her. Then her lover faces serious problem to satisfy her lady-love. It seems, she even does not know what she actually wants. Thus the fiancé cannot please his dear fiancée.

Appropriate is a matter of perception. Perception is quite unique in nature. As such it differs from person to person that makes individual difference. Also it varies with various cultures. So before implementation of anything concerned person and culture should be considered meticulously lest in the mid-way the project is not hindered or ultimately stopped. It causes frustration coupled with huge loss of money, time and energy as well. This mishap disheartens to take any project further in future.

Appropriate has a good relation with decency and etiquette. Both are applicable in every sphere of life. Protocol directs and dictates the foreign relation among the nations. Here appropriate measure is very important.

Cleanliness is next to Godliness is a wise saying. The clean atmosphere of any religious place awakes in mind the presence of Almighty God. A person feels comfort here. He becomes happy. He enjoys divine grace. Thus clean is always good. It paves the way to achieve greatness. They say where goodness ends, greatness begins.

Clean has much effect in every sphere of life. A clean person attracts all and everybody. He whose attitude is clear cut draws respect. A person who plays in straight bat is loved by all. A person throws garbage in any dirty place. But that very person cannot thereby will not unclean any clean surface. He will experience psychological brake that will resist him not to create nuisance in any clean place. Here no notice or vigilance is required. Here lies the power and triumph of cleanliness.

What is appropriate to someone may not be approved by another one. So before sanction, where third party's approval is a must, pre-approval is the best strategy. As such they say 'look before you leap'. Thus there is pre-paid. Also there is post-paid. Someone likes pre-paid. His intention is always pre. Someone likes post-paid. His intention is post. Sometimes he pays never. It seems pre-paid is better than post-paid to get protection from financial penalty or higher payment.

Appropriate may be personal. It may be public. It may be universal. In case of personal choice voice of head of the family is final. In case of public affair there may be choice of someone but voice of majority is considered as public which is final. Tradition, custom are appropriate as universal which everybody obeys and does not take the risk of change for uncertainty, injustice and fear.

What is suitable for adult is not appropriate for children. To enjoy adult picture maturity is required. Immaturity relates with children. Here maturity is not appropriate in innocent period of life. Maturity deprives a teen ager from enjoyment. This loss is forever and nostalgic in nature since childhood never comes back.

Time moves forward. Age moves gradually. Man becomes older. He becomes busy. The grown up person cannot enjoy like a child. As such if a person does not enjoy in childhood then he cannot enjoy later on. He laments forever.

In patriarchal society age of bride is less than groom. Here senior woman is not appropriate for a junior man. The reason thus considered is that the woman becomes older than man earlier and loses sexual urge though the husband still hankers after sexual intercourse. If the husband does not get it then he becomes psychologically ill and sometimes is involved in extra-marital affair that leads to social problem.

Obviously, modern youths do not obey this restriction. They are interested more for instant gain. They seldom think for constant. Such a jet-age fellow thinks for present. Future is uncertain. Present is certain. To them certain is more appropriate than uncertain.

Conversion is very important in human life. A shrewd politician can convert a crisis into an opportunity. Someone may utter an inappropriate word or may behave inappropriately. If the person is callous then he gets punishment. In contrast, if the person is a talented one then he can explain his inappropriate attitude as appropriate and relevant one. The talented person intentionally behaved inappropriately just to draw attention. Thus talented person wins everywhere in every age.

Time changes. Season changes. Mood changes. Man changes. This is equally true in appropriate. What is appropriate today may not be appropriate tomorrow. Everything is controlled by many factors. If one of the parameters changes appropriate also changes. Parameters are known and unknown. Measures can be taken as per change of the known parameters which is not possible in case of unknown parameters. Unknown parameters render the situation more uncertain and no action or nothing can be done.

Conclusion

An author writes. It is his democratic right. He writes what he thinks appropriate. An editor publishes. It is also his democratic right. An editor may not publish any writing. It is his more democratic right. In this regard an author should not mind anything. He should not pass any bad remarks against the editor. He should not propagate any adverse comments against the journal. An editor receives many articles. He compares all submissions. He publishes those articles which he thinks appropriate for his journal. He has to face tough competition with his rivals. Rubbish publication defames a journal. It experiences the dogma of sub-standard which cannot be compensated easily and regain its previous status as well. The author does not know all such matters. He should submit appropriate submission. Here lies the uniqueness of appropriate rather than unique appropriate.

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